

Academic Resilience and Learning Styles among Higher Secondary School Students

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Abstract - This study investigates the association between academic resilience and learning styles among higher secondary school students in Kozhikode, Kerala. A sample of 300 students was selected using stratified sampling based on gender, locale, stream of study, and type of management. Standardized tools – the Academic Resilience Scale and Learning Styles Inventory – were used for data collection. The findings revealed significant differences in academic resilience based on learning styles and demographic variables such as gender and stream of study. A notable association between academic resilience and learning styles was observed. The study emphasizes the role of individualized learning approaches to enhance academic resilience and academic outcomes.

Keywords - Academic Resilience, Learning Styles, Higher Secondary Students, VARK Model, Educational Psychology.

I. Introduction

In a competitive educational landscape, students often face pressure that affects their academic performance and mental well-being. While some struggle, others thrive despite adversities – a phenomenon termed "academic resilience." Understanding how learning styles contribute to this resilience can help educators tailor interventions that support student success.

II. Literature Review

Martin and Marsh (2006) described academic resilience as the ability to maintain high performance despite challenges. Learning styles, such as visual, auditory, kinesthetic, and reading/writing preferences (Fleming, 1987), shape how students process information. Prior studies have suggested that aligning teaching methods with learning styles can improve motivation and outcomes (Dunn & Dunn, 1989; Gohel, 2009).

III. Methodology

A descriptive survey method was employed. The sample comprised 300 higher secondary students from various schools in Kozhikode. Stratification was done based on gender, locale, type of school management, and academic stream. Two tools were used: Academic Resilience Scale and Learning Styles Inventory, both developed by

Salim & Syamaladevi (2021). Data were analyzed using mean, standard deviation, t-tests, ANOVA, and chi-square tests.

Results and Discussion

Students predominantly exhibited visual and kinesthetic learning styles. Moderate to high resilience levels were observed across the sample. Female students and those from the science stream scored higher in resilience. A statistically significant relationship was found between learning styles and resilience. Students with kinesthetic and visual styles demonstrated stronger resilience attributes.

IV. Conclusion and Implications

The study concludes that learning styles significantly influence academic resilience. Teachers should consider these styles while designing curriculum and instructional methods. Educational policies should incorporate resilience training as part of academic planning to help students manage stress and challenges effectively.

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